

Changing Media Ownership Patterns of Indian Media

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Abstract

This chapter discusses the changing media ownerships trends amidst the challenges of digitalized world and globalization. Media the fourth pillar plays an important role in a democratic process of our country. Media convergence has given rise to media multiplicity, diversity and concentration. The amalgamation of different media ownerships has weakened the democratic value of transforming the news content on ethical grounds. The opening of media markets at global has lead to inter corporate investments. Emergence of conglomerates, private ownerships has not only brought vested interests and goals but foreign investments are also hindrance to nation's security and sovereignty. The weakening of traditional media boundaries and the rise of participatory audience has lead to varied concerns among academicians and policy makers to separate the editorial governance and corporate ownerships.

Keywords:

Media ownerships, journalism trends, globalization, digitalization

Introduction

Media is the fourth pillar of Indian democratic process and plays a crucial role in the democratic process. In a democratic country like ours, the role of media is expected to have more freedom, multiplicity, plurality, in-depth, fair information and coverage both in the structure and content. The role of media to inform, communicate and educate has changed drastically and media has emerged as a global and competitive market.

According to Schlosberg, 2016, Ownership refers to the various forms of governance associated with particular ownership structures, while the owners of media constitute the individuals and companies that wield influence over their organization (p. 8). Due to scales of mergers and volumes in ownerships, it has created interest academic research in media multiplicity, concentration, diversity and amalgamation leading to plaguing the democratic values and ethics of journalism profession.

The amalgamation of different media ownerships is worldwide and has become a continuous practice. In the Indian democratic system, the ownership patterns of Indian Media have been changing with the changing times.

With changing times media ownerships patterns needs to be reviewed from various perspective.

There has been media corporatization, deregulation of media ownerships rules because of privatization of state owned media openings and mushroom growth of media outlets due to satellite and internet which gave shape to new media and various other media platforms. The opening of media markets at global levels is leading to

homogenization of culture which would have long term effects and destruct the cultural values. Convergence of media due to technological advancement has raised concerns among policy makers, academicians and stakeholders to separate the editorial governance and corporate ownerships.

Factors influencing change in ownership patterns

In earlier times information was controlled and dominated by western conglomerates but with the advent of new communication technologies, globalization, digitalization and new media flow of information has been democratized which has changed the distribution, consumption pattern drastically over the period of time. A shift toward concentration and "tycoon" ownership emerged in the second half of the 19th century, particularly in the United Kingdom (Curran, 2002) and the United States (Machesney, 2003).

With the change in shape of global political and economic landscape in 1970's and 80's, the structure and ownership of media industry has also changed. New communication technologies have increased the fragmentation of local media industries. It not only increased the competition among media markets but also for wide audience attention.

The main areas of concern with change in ownership patterns; it is plaguing journalistic practices, media diversity and autonomy which is further affecting news content and distribution. According to Part 2015, media proprietors for their vested interests generally try to manipulate the news content. Before 1980s, media was mainly controlled by public sector in many nations. The structure and landscape of media ownerships

changed drastically in 1980s and 1990s when government controls were fragmented in many countries.

Arrival of FDI in the Indian Media Landscape: In June 2002, Indian Print industry, the union cabinet allowed 26 percent FDI liberating to 49 percent in 2005. Indian media is different as compared to developed countries due to varied languages, geographical area, heterogeneous audience and various other factors. Mushroom growth of satellite, mergers, digitalization and making structural changes in media control and ownerships since 1990's.

Media Ownerships and Journalism

Earlier there were restrictions in multiple ownerships but over the period of time the media industry started spreading its wings. With concentration, globalization and digitalization there is drastic change in the democratic value of news. The four main type of ownerships are chain, cross, conglomerate and vertical integration.

Chain ownerships are formed when two or more mediums are controlled by same media organizations to manage the finances, administration and other assets centrally such as Hindustan Times has 13 editions under the umbrella of HT media and similarly Aaj Tak and Headlines Today are two channels under the India Today Group. Vertical ownership is promoting different organizations simultaneously to cut the expenses which hinders the attention on one particular media because monetary investments are made at various media platforms.

Cross media and Conglomerate media ownership in Indian Media has caused number of cross investment interest to play around. Media

Conglomerate ownership in which large number of media outlets are owned such as television, radio etc. hinders the democratic value of news. The biggest example is BBC. In this type of ownership, no doubt the internal capital is build but business management is not done equally. As mentioned by Madhav 2008 conglomerate ownership supports the other businesses of the proprietors and in this kind of ownership pattern ethics and standards are often being conceded.

With the introduction of cable in the beginning of 1990s, the Indian television industry has changed drastically. As far as print media industry is concerned most of the Indian newspapers conglomerates are either owned by the families or individuals. Due to lack of rules and regulations in cross media ownerships mainly all the newspapers have entered into electronic media as well.

As far as at global level, ownership patterns are distinct which can be categorized into state, private which includes families and others which covers community. A World Bank study mentioned that around 60 percent of newspapers and 34 percent of the entire television stations are family controlled. State ownership is too massive. The state controlled almost 26 percent of newspapers and 60 percent of television stations. The state owned a enormous 72 percent segment of the top radio positions. Whereas only four percent of media organisations were controlled by others counting two percent member owned and less than two percent have other ownership arrangements. More than two dozen nations have government controls on daily newspapers and nearly 50 countries have state domination on television. Television has considerably greater concentrations of state ownership than newspapers.

Conclusion

With the concentration, globalization and digitalization there is drastic change in the democratic value of news. Rethinking of sociology of media ownership visa-vis the characteristics of media, especially mass media is a need of an hour. The changing media ownership patterns have great impact on its freedom, autonomy, content and overall future of journalism. The Indian media industry with varied ownership has a threat on its press freedom and diversity.

Media players are mainly with what is produced –the content, how it is produced the medium and how it is produced the technology and for whom it is produced the target audience or the consumers. Media ownerships are directly linked with the economic and business activities of any organizations New technologies have blurred the role of gatekeepers and newsrooms. It has increased the competitions among media outlets and varied ownerships thereby weakening the traditional market landscape and structure.

According to Picard and Dal Zotto , “various complaints concerning ownership have nothing to do with ownership, somewhat the complaints are regarding commercialized nature of media and the pursuit of economic rewards.”p.56

In the era of overload of information there is need for more stringent rules and regulations visa- vis ownerships and content produced by media in order to safeguard the core principles and values of journalism. No doubt, all media outlets should optimize self regulation and self censorship while operating in digitalized world but there is also a strong need for reframing the legal media regulations in India in order to ensure in transparency in varied media ownerships, structure and landscape.

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